

Ohio Principal's Behavior Leadership on Teacher's Professional Commitment: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Ohio Principal's Behavior Leadership on Teacher Professional Commitment. The principal's behavior leadership is one of the components that support schools to achieve educational goals with good quality, how to lead in influencing and mobilizing subordinates, selecting and developing the character of each individual, carrying out communication to all elements of the organization, motivating subordinates, making decisions and supervising subordinates. Then there is a personal relationship built by the principal with the teacher, the structure of the division of teacher duties through consideration and initiating structure, to the teacher's professional commitment at school. The research method in this article uses the library research method (Library Research) this research method deals with library data collection methods. The data collection technique in this study uses documentation and the data analysis technique of this study uses critical analysis, which is critical in nature, generally starting from certain views or values believed by the researcher in the problem of the influence of the principal's ohio behavioral leadership on the commitment of the teacher profession. Through the commitment of professional teachers based on expertise, competence and specialist knowledge obtained through certain education, it will improve the quality and quality of education.

KEYWORDS: Behavior Leadership, Ohio Principal's, Teacher Professional Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Background of this Article

School as an educational institution is a means of implementing learning services and educational processes, expected to function all existing resources effectively in achieving goals and efficiency in the use of resources. Schools are not only used as a gathering place between teachers and students but a very complex and dynamic system. The principal's task as an educational leader is responsible for managing the school optimally to achieve goals [1]. The success of the school in carrying out what has been planned or organized, needs to be supported by the principal's ability. Principal leadership behavior is one of the components that support schools to achieve educational goals with good quality [2]. Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that leadership behavior is a performance possessed by the principal to influence, mobilize and guide other individuals in order to achieve a common goal. The main role of the principal is to build an active teaching and learning atmosphere, provide direction, delegate authority, and make decisions through collaboration with the school [3]. Leadership behavior is the leader's way of influencing and mobilizing subordinates, selecting and developing the character of each individual, communicating to all elements of the organization, motivating subordinates, making decisions and supervising subordinates [4]. Based on the above understandings, it can be concluded that the principal's leadership behavior is the principal's activities in influencing, coordinating, mobilizing and communicating with all school members, including teachers, education personnel, parents and students to achieve a previously agreed goal so as to increase the commitment of a better teacher profession. Good principal leadership will encourage school leaders to appreciate the increase in teachers' professional commitment. Professional teachers must be committed to carrying out their professional duties, namely educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating as a form of responsibility as a teacher [5]. Teacher commitment is a commitment that is determined for one's work as identification and involvement in a profession and exerting efforts to maintain membership in the profession. Professional commitment is the level of individual loyalty to his profession with his job commitment, the level of acceptance of the values of the chosen job or line of work, and the willingness to maintain work. From the above opinion, the commitment of the teacher profession is the ability to understand oneself and one's duties and responsibilities as a teacher in educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating as a teacher who is committed to carrying out his professional duties, the level of individual loyalty to his profession with his job commitment.

Ohio Behavioral Theory Leadership

Ohio behavioral theory leadership is based on increasing teacher professional commitment supported by behavioral leadership through (1) consideration, (2) initiating structure. Consideration the extent to which a leader acts kindly showing the attention and welfare of teachers, initiating structure the extent to which a leader determines and structures the role of the principal and the duties of teachers in increasing teacher commitment, teacher commitment will increase directly and indirectly through commitment to the school as a social unit, commitment to school academic activities, commitment to students as unique individuals, commitment to creating quality learning, so that in this case it is expected to be able to encourage the improvement of behavioral leadership ohio head towards teacher professional commitment has a good correlation and can run optimally in accordance with the desired educational goals [6].

Importance and Gap of Literature Review

Ohio principals' leadership behavior will increase the teacher's professional commitment. In this research, the author focuses on the leadership behavior of Ohio principals by identifying the leadership behavior of Ohio principals towards commitment to the teaching profession, which can be practiced to increase teacher commitment in achieving goals. This idea focuses on consideration and initiating structure. So, through this review journal, I will examine in more depth the leadership behavior of Ohio school principals to add to the development of new theories regarding the theory of Ohio leadership behavior in schools, because so far the research has been the same only focuses on companies and universities, but there is still very little research on this in schools. Therefore, I am very interested in conducting this research.

METHODS

The writing of this article uses a library research method (Library Research) this method deals with library data collection methods. The data sources used in this research are articles. Sources of data obtained from searching national and international articles on google scholar. After reviewing the literature in accordance with this theme and the author selected 8 articles taken according to the criteria with the keywords "Behavioral Leadership" and "Teacher Professional Commitment" then the article is analyzed as a whole in the discussion written in this article. Data collection techniques in this study used documentation and data analysis in this study using critical analysis where this analysis is critical in nature generally departing from certain views or values believed by researchers related to the problem of the influence of the principal's ohio behavioral leadership on the commitment of the teacher profession. The search ranged from 2018 to 2023 and identified a total of 6.350 studies and articles from Asia.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Type

Research designs used in this scientific research are quantitative method.

2. Type of Intervention

The main study in scientific research is the leadership behavior of Ohio principals towards the commitment of the teaching profession. Journals that meet the criteria Ohio principal's inclusion and leadership behavior themes towards commitment to the teaching profession are reviewed further. Criteria for selected journals what will be reviewed are journals with the theme of Ohio school principals' leadership behavior towards teacher professional commitment. Inclusion criteria for this article are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion
1. Ohio Principal's	1. Leadership Style
2. Behavior Leadership	2. Company/College
3. School	3. College Leaders
4. Teacher	4. Dissertation/Thesis

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

The following is a review of the research that has been carried out. This analysis was conducted broadly on the leadership behavior principals regarding the commitment to the teaching profession. The literature review that researchers have carried out is as follows:

Table 2. Results of Literature Review

No.	Title	Author & year	& Country	Method	Sample	Results
1.	Relationship between School Principals' Leadership Behaviors and Teachers' Organizational Trust	Mehmet Kars, Yusuf Inandi (2018) [7]	Turki	Quantitative research	Teachers	The study show that democratic principal behaviors affect not only teachers principal trust but also their trust in colleagues, students, and parents. Therefore, school principals should take education seminars to increase their awareness about the importance democratic leadership.
2.	The Influence of Principal Leadership and Organizational Culture on Teachers' Commitment in Carrying Out Their Tasks.	Asmaul Husnah, Edi Harapan, Rohana (2021) [15]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	Examining principal leadership and organizational culture on teacher commitment in carrying out tasks shows that principal leadership has a significant effect on teacher commitment.
3.	The Effect of Organizational Culture, Job Satisfaction and Principal Leadership Style on Job Commitment of Teachers of MAN 1 and MAN 2 Pekanbaru.	Herlina, Zulkarnaini, Murni Baheram (2020) [8]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	There is a direct influence of the principal's leadership style on organizational culture, job satisfaction, and teacher work commitment.

4.	The Impact of Leadership, School Climate and Achievement Motivation in Improving Teacher Commitment.	Lukman Hakim, Bukman Lian, Alhadi Yan Putra, (2021) [9]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	That principal leadership, school climate, achievement motivation together have a significant effect on teacher commitment
5.	Increasing Teachers' Commitment to the Profession through Organizational Culture Development and Job Satisfaction	Isep Djuanda (2021) [10]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	There is a significant positive relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction with commitment of teachers to the profession
6.	The Effect of School Culture and Work Motivation on the Commitment of Vocational Teachers in Meranti Islands	Tri Sofia Yanreta, Zulfan Saam, Makhdalena (2019) [11]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	That the proposed structural model is accepted school culture has a direct and meaningful influence on teacher work motivation, school culture has a positive influence on teacher commitment.
7.	Job Satisfaction as a Mediator between Directive and Participatory Leadership Styles toward Organizational Commitment	Humuntal Banjarnahor, Wesly Hutabarat (2018) [11]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	Principals play a very important role in determining the quality of education in schools. The success of the principals to mobilize all potential in the school environment is highly dependent on the leadership styles.
8.	Correlation of Principal Leadership Type and School Culture to Teacher Commitment	N.P Widya Oktaviavi, M.G Rini Kristiantari (2021) [13]	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Teachers	Showed that there was a significant correlation between the type of leadership of the principal and school culture on teacher commitment.

2. Discussion

Based on the review of the articles collected, the Ohio leadership behavior theory, the existence of a personal relationship built by the principal with the teacher and the structure of the division of teacher duties through consideration and initiating structure [14]. The quality of a leader determines the success of the institution he leads, including educational institutions. Because successful leadership is led to the goals set. In connection with that, the leader is able to manage the institution he leads, is able to anticipate changes, is able to correct deficiencies and weaknesses and is able to bring the institution is the key to success for the organization. Therefore, a principal is needed who has insight into the future and adequate ability to drive the organization in one of the schools. in line with Ohio's leadership behavior theory, there is a personal relationship built by the principal with teachers and the structure of the division of teacher duties through input, process and output. Based on Ohio Theory According to views leadership behavior in two behavioral dimensions, namely consideration and initiating structure: Consideration is the degree to which a leader acts friendly showing concern for subordinates and paying attention to welfare [15]. With indicators: doing good to subordinates, making time to listen to subordinates' problems, providing support to subordinates to advance, exchanging ideas with subordinates for important matters before implementation, accepting subordinate suggestions and treating subordinates carefully. Initiating Structure is the degree to which a leader determines and structures his own role and the roles of subordinates in the direction of articulating an attractive vision, increasing follower commitment, increasing follower effort, improving the quality and productivity of achieving formal group goals, leader behavior is more likely to be concerned with organizational goals than good treatment of subordinates. With indicators: leader behavior that often provides constructive criticism of inappropriate work, emphasizes the importance of time defined in terms of individual characteristics, professional commitment of teacher leadership behavior, interaction patterns, role relationships, follower perceptions and their effects on followers and school culture. Stating that leadership is a process that arises in a group and includes a common goal and influencing followers. [17]. Good principal leadership will encourage school leaders to appreciate the increase in teachers' professional commitment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature review study that the author has done, from the writing of this article, the author can conclude that the leadership behavior of the ohio principal towards the commitment of the teacher profession, each variable has dimensions and supporting indicators to realize educational goals, increasing the commitment of the teacher profession is supported by leadership behavior through consideration the extent to which a leader acts friendly showing the attention and welfare of teachers, initiating structure the extent to which a leader determines and structures the role of the principal and the duties of the teacher in increasing teacher commitment, teacher commitment will increase directly and indirectly through commitment to the school as a social unit, commitment to school academic activities, commitment to students as unique individuals, commitment to creating quality learning, so that in this case it is expected to be able to encourage an increase in behavioral leadership ohio head to teacher professional commitment has a good correlation and can run optimally in accordance with educational goals.

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